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Effect Of Tax Revenue Of Market And Petty Traders On Capital Expenditure In Osun State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of tax revenue of market (men and women) and petty traders on capital expenditure in Osun state, Nigeria. Secondary data were obtained from Osun State Internal Revenue Service and Ministry of Finance through Office of the Accountant General from 2016 to 2024. Multiple regression was used to analyse the data. The result revealed taxes from market (men and women) traders had positive and significant effect on capital expenditure ($t-v= 1.994, p<0.01$) while taxes from petty traders had insignificant effect on capital expenditure ($t-v= 0.1435, p>0.05$) respectively. The study concluded that tax revenue from market traders (men and women) significantly influence the capital expenditure of Osun state. The study recommended that tax collection from the informal sector (market traders) could be enhanced when government educates the informal operators, strengthens tax laws, emphasize on adequate records.

Keywords: Tax revenue, capital expenditure, market traders, petty traders

INTRODUCTION

The Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) of the States encompasses both tax and non-tax sources of income generated by the government in the areas of their jurisdiction. According to the National Bureau of Statistics Approved List for Collection (Act Amendment) Order, 2015 (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2017), The Nigeria Governors' Forum Secretariat (NGFS), which is the administrative and technical arm of the NGF, has facilitated numerous reform programmes across Nigerian States and charged the State Governors to make greater effort to improve their IGR. The secretariat suggested that since June 2014 fiscal issues have become more pressing, so the Nigerian Governors' Forum (NGF) organised a workshop to support the search for increased IGR and broaden the options.

Recently, the State Governments of the NGF asked for financial assistance from the Federal Government as they had difficulty paying their workers and other on-going expenses. To address this, the Federal Government provided a bailout of N1.75 trillion to the affected States (including Osun) to cover payroll costs and other recurrent expenditure (Deloitte, 2016; DMO, 2017).

Abomaye-Nimenibo et al., (2017) have also stressed that taxes are a compulsory contribution to the government, made directly or indirectly, and those who refuse to pay can face sanctions. They further argued that, taxes are an important source of increasing government revenue, they can be progressive in nature and used to promote equity. The Government use tax revenue to provide public goods and services that would otherwise not be available in a free market. Therefore, taxation plays a key role in economic growth and development in Nigeria. Thus, in Osun state, the informal sector and their activities make up about 70-80% of the economy (Adesanya, 2016). The Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2016), described the informal sector, as "grey economy", that has a major impact on the economic development of Nigeria, this contribution continues to increase. Also, (Asaleye et al., 2018) emphasised that, informal sector helps to reduce the high level of unemployment in Nigeria providing jobs for around 48 million people. These factors above demonstrate the importance of the informal sector for the economic growth and development of Nigeria. Therefore.

informal sector tax revenue categorised as (levies from trading associations, market traders, small vendors and petty traders). The informal enterprises engage in coordinated commercial activity, such as bazaar traders, restaurants, and small ad hoc factories. They may or may not have a discernible organisational structure, with operations (and employment) that grows or shrinks, depending upon the demand for the enterprises' outputs or services. They are built around an entrepreneur who engages in a series of spot market transactions with customers, suppliers and workers, depending upon demand

Awa, (2022) established that the Nigerian informal sector such as market traders has a significant impact on the nation's total output, despite having low productivity and that informal labour is a major roadblock to sustainable growth in emerging markets and developing countries. This is because informal firms are not making a contribution to the tax base, tend to stay small, with low productivity and few options for obtaining financing for expansion. As a result, economic growth in regions or countries with high levels of informal labour will remain stunted. Informal workers are more likely to be impoverished than those in the formal sector due to the lack of contractual agreements and social protection, in addition to a lower level of education.

Similarly, Topal and Sahin, (2017) stated that regulatory effectiveness of informal sector is assessed by assessing the government's capacity and competence to establish well-thought-out policies and regulations that are essential for economic development. This incorporates the utilization of tax policies such as tax rates, deductions, exemptions, tax holidays, and other forms of tax reliefs to motivate firms, create an environment conducive to their survival and thereby promote economic growth and development in the country.

The tax component of IGR is a significant source of income for governments to fulfil their responsibilities to citizens. Tax income contributes to economic growth and development, stabilizing the economy, and managing economic fluctuations, such as inflation and deflation. It also helps to allocate resources fairly, combat poverty and promote socio-economic development in the Country. (Ofoegbu & Oliver, 2016) argued that taxation is an important instrument of economic reform and a vital tool for economic development. Tax revenue has become a major funding source for Nigeria's growing economic activities. (Adegboyega et al., 2019) asserted that the cost of governance has gone up and income from federal allocation has decreased in recent years, hence the governments in Nigeria have sought to increase their revenue base. Therefore, government expenditures usually tend to increase astronomically as an economy becomes large due to the wider scope of its activities.) The capital budget takes care of expenses necessary to procure capital assets (Frank & Kereotu, 2020). Thus, governments of all kinds, in respect of their size and level of intentions, showcased a similar increasing tendency of public expenditure. Thus, without revenue, for government to cater for the yarns of citizenries in term of spending money on capital project will difficult

Osun state capital expenditure has continuous increased due to increase in population and problems link with urbanization often aggravate the force to increase in government spending (Onifade et al 2019) while the huge income from inform sector and its influence has not been felt on the economy of the state in terms of infrastructure and social amenities are still backward and decay that collapse of the country.

Osun state economic potential is constrained by many structural issues, including inadequate infrastructure, obstacles to investment, and limited internal generated revenue. These affect economic development of the state to be accompanied by improvements in infrastructure, as well as social, political, and institutional factors to facilitate transformation of the economy through taxes collected by taxpayers (Erero, 2021)

Informal enterprises rarely invest in productivity-enhancing equipment, upgrade workers' skills, or achieve economies of scale, and tend to function on razor-thin margins. They have no recourse to legal protection should their customers renege on payment, and can offer no form of security to their employees, pay no taxes, and ignore minimum wage regulations (ILO, 2019). However, Adesoji and Chike, (2016), observed that the current state of infrastructures to promote economic growth and development in most of the states across nation is nothing to write home about, perhaps, due to political and economic reasons.

The growing cost of government administration together with declining income has taught governments in Nigeria to improve revenue base (Adegboyega, et al, 2019). The informal sector has

presented the hope of engendering additional income to compensate for the shortfall in tax revenue. The informal economy is a concept originally introduced by the International Labour Organisation and is described as “a way of doing things” and has seven drivers which include ease of entry; reliance on indigenous resources; family ownership; small-scale operation; labour intensive and adaptive technologies; unregulated and competitive markets (Olabisi et al 2020). However, governments in developing countries, including Nigeria, do not recognize the crucial role that informal sectors can play in the economic development of their countries. A lot of government policies have shown to work against the informal sector by not encouraging productivity and growth that would result in them entering the formal economy. Simply put, there is inadequate government support for the informal sector which limits tax collection .

Several studies such as (Awa, 2022; Etim and Daramola,2020; Mpofu, 2021; Olabisi et al, 2020; Omodero,2020; Sultana et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2020; Adisa et al., 2019 and Obara & Nangih, 2017) have conducted studies on informal sector and some of the above researchers focused on different countries as whole, while other focused in Lagos, Ebonyi state and scanty of them focuses in Osun State but they did not consider taxes from market traders (men and women) and petty traders . Given the above, It is against this background, this study is attempt to filled the gap by examine the effect of tax revenue of market (men and women) and petty traders on capital expenditure in Osun state, Nigeria.

The following research questions were raised:What is the effect of taxes from market traders (men and women) on capital expenditure of Osun state?How does tax revenue from petty traders affect capital expenditure in Osun state

Specifically, objectives are to: examine the effect of taxes from market traders (men and women) trader on capital expenditure of Osun state; assess the effect of tax revenue from petty traders on capital expenditure in Osun state. The study will contribute to knowledge by adding value to tax policy and revenue administration process/procedure in Osun state. This study will be of importance to government, by providing information on what causes tax payment problems and how it can be curb. The study will also provide appropriate approach for preventing revenue leakages in term of revenue loss and mismanagement of revenue generation in all agencies of government which may directly have positive impact on the capital expenditure of Osun State. Furthermore, the findings of this study will pave way for effective strategies to be adopted in capturing and payment of all revenues into government coffers without the intermedaiator.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Capital expenditure

Government Capital expenditure refers to expenses incurred by the government on developmental projects such as equipment, building, health facilities, education, roads equipment, and machinery e .t .c. It also includes the expenses incurred in acquiring tangible assets such as land and investment by the government that will give expected returns in the future. The capital budget takes care of expenses necessary to procure capital assets (Frank & Kereotu, 2020). Thus, governments of all kinds, in respect of their size and level of intentions, showcased a similar increasing tendency of public expenditure. Hence, the government intervention in various sectors of the economy resultant in government capital expenditure increases in the economy. Wagner theory states further that the growth of the economy was the basic factor that determines the growth of the public sector (Owui, et al 2020)

Market Traders (Men and Women)

Market traders have shops in the same and different markets in prominent towns in the State. There are periodic markets outside and within the cities, while the periodic market places serve the traditional needs; the trading centres serve as bridges between export enclaves and the produce markets in the rural areas (Gilson, 2015). There are normally periodic market places in rural areas and daily marketplaces are dominant in urban areas by market men and women. Because a higher proportion of women than men work in the informal sector, taxes on the informal sector fall on women more than men. For example, taxes on market traders affect women disproportionately in places where the majority of these traders are women, such as sub-Saharan Africa. In Nigeria in

2018, 80% of women and only 50% of men worked in the informal sector. A 2018 study found that 95% of informal women traders paid some kind of tax, whether national presumptive tax or local taxes including market fees. Half of these women paid both national and local taxes, and a higher proportion of taxes was paid by those earning relatively less (Sempere, 2018). The major sources of informal tax revenue are registration fee, renewal fee, trade permit, tenement rate and market levy. These are collected from market traders (male and female), petty traders, small vendors, associations and small entrepreneurs.

Petty Trading (PT)

This is an economic activity that involves the buying and selling of goods and services on a smaller scale, from agricultural products to imported consumable goods. This activity is an important part of the informal sector and is responsible for providing consumers with goods that the formal sector is unable to, such as fruits, vegetables, groundnuts, biscuits, spoons, pans, cigarettes, cosmetics, jewellery, and ladies' bags and wallets, as well as second-hand clothes (David, 2016; and Musa & Acheampong, 2014). Nevertheless, informal workers and businesses are often taxed. This is done through numerous types of fees, charges and licensing costs, which may be levied locally, state or both. Often these taxes and fees fail to take account of one another, and overlap, resulting in the payer being taxed multiple times. They tend to be based on very general estimates and are commonly flat-rated, which usually produces regressive results. A common type of local taxation of the informal sector that affects poor people is the market taxes and fees levied on market stallholders. Many examples of taxation of the informal sector are 'presumptive' taxes. These are estimates of tax payable, based on simple indicators of business performance (such as turnover) or on visible characteristics such as the number of seats in a bus, and often paid as lump-sums (Dube & Casale, 2016)

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Adolf Wagner's Theory of Increasing State Activities

This was named after the German political economist Adolph Wagner (1835-1917) in 1890, who developed a law of increasing state activity after empirical analysis on Western Europe at the end of the 19th century. He argued that government expenditure is a function of increased industrialization and economic development. Wagner stated that during the industrialization process, as the real income per capita of a nation increases, the share of public expenditures in total expenditures increases. The law states that the advent of modern industrial society will result in increasing political pressure for social progress and increased allowance for social consideration by industry.

Wagner (1893) designed three focal bases for the increased in state expenditure. Firstly, during industrialization process, public sector activity will replace private sector activity. State functions like administrative and protective functions will increase. Secondly, governments needed to provide cultural and welfare services like education, public health, old age pension or retirement insurance, food subsidy, natural disaster aid, environmental protection programs and other welfare functions. Thirdly, increased industrialization will bring out technological change and large firms that tend to monopolize. Governments will have to offset these effects by providing social and merit goods through budgetary means.

In other words, Wagner's law states that, as per capita income of an economy grows, the relative size of public expenditure grows, the relative size of public expenditure grows along with it. As the economy grows, there will be increase in the number of urban centers, with the associated social vices such as; crime, which require the intervention of the government, to reduce such activities to the barest minimum. Large urban centers also require internal security, to maintain law and order. These interventions by the government have cost, leading to increase in public expenditure in the economy. (Ogba, 1999).

2.2.2 Musgrave Theory of Public Expenditure Growth

Musgrave (1959) posits that changes in the income elasticity of demand for public services exist at three stages of per-capita income of the citizenry. Firstly, at a low level of per-capita income that is typical of pre-industrial societies in developing economies. At this level, demand for public services tends to be generally very low because nearly all incomes are devoted to satisfaction of primary needs and public expenditure is always at a low level. Secondly, when per-capita income starts rising, a demand for public services supplied by the public sector such as health, education,

electricity, transport services and other social amenities will also rising which engenders the need for government to increase expenditure on them. The last stage is at the higher levels of per capita income typical of advanced economies. Here the rate of public sector growth tends to fall as the more basic needs are satisfied.

Musgrave (1959) noted that in the early stages of economic development, the rate of growth of public expenditure will be very high, because government provides the basic infrastructural facilities (social overhead). And most of these projects are capital intensive, therefore, the spending of the government will increase steadily. The investment in education, health, roads, electricity, and water supply are necessities that can launch the economy from the traditional stage to the take off stage of economic development making government to spend an increasing amount with time in order to develop an egalitarian society (Ogba, 1999).

However, despite the fact that the Musgrave theory is quite plausible, it has one strong limitation which was admitted by Musgrave. The theory was unable to clearly predict the size of public expenditure in the later stages even though the stages of development approach are undoubtedly applicable in early development phase. This is because there is a change in private consumption patterns because of rising per capita income during the late industrialization stages and individual need which determines if public expenditure will rise or decline.

Underpinning Theory

This study was anchored on two theories that is, Wagner's Theory of Increasing State Activities and Peacock and Wiseman Theory of public expenditure because Wagner's Theory opined that government expenditure is triggered by public revenue and an increase in public revenue empowers the government to execute its spending and ultimately increase government on capital expenditure. In the same vein, the theory relates that the capacity of the government to expand the base of capital projects is always limited by the failure of the citizenry to pay their taxes as and when due. The study also supported by Peacock and Wiseman theory of public expenditure because the theory attributed the growth of public expenditure to revenue generation, indicating that an increase in national income will endanger increase in the expenditure pattern of nations. Although there was disaggregation of views as regards what caused an increase in government expenditures, the inference that could be derived from the theory is that public expenditure is always dependent on revenue generation. This theory is relevant to this study on the basis that expenditure patterns of both Nigeria are contingent on the amount of revenue generated from their various sources of revenue

2.3 Empirical Review

Obara and Nangih (2017) assessed the effect of taxing the informal sector in Nigeria with a focus on the River state. Data collected were analysed using Kruskal Wallis and Chi-square tests to revealed that taxing the informal sector boosted revenue generation and positively affected the economic development of developing states in Nigeria

Yelwa and Adam (2017) reported the impact of the informal sector on the economic growth of Nigeria between the period of 1980–2014. The study discovered that despite the commendable impact of the informal sector on economic growth, this relationship is not linear. The authors suggested that government should integrate informal sector businesses into the formal sector, and regulate the sector because of its potential to increase fiscal revenue through tax collection.

A study conducted by Ogundajo, et al., (2019) investigated the effect of informal economy on generation of tax revenue in Nigeria. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The findings revealed that informal sector (tax assessment and collection technique, tax compliance level, informal sector financial acquisition and economic activities of informal sector) significantly affected revenue generation through tax in Nigeria.

Usman et al., (2019) studied the challenges of effective tax collection from the informal sector in Nigeria over the period 2014 – 2018. The researchers revealed that issues such as reliance on cash based transactions, absence of required records; lack of awareness; inadequate information; lack of government support and weak tax laws are some of the challenges preventing effective tax collection from the informal sector.

Guillermo and Deyve (2019) examined the size of informal economy in Peru, Latin America and OCDE countries as well as estimated the impact of the informal economy on tax revenue and economic growth. The study adopted the Multiple Indicator and Multiple Cause (MIMIC) model.

The results showed that the estimated average size of informal economy on tax revenue as a percentage of GDP was 37.4 % in Peru, in Latin America it was 34 % and in OCDE countries – 19.89 % representing less than half of the average in Latin America.

Omodero (2020) investigated the influence of the informal sector and graft on income accruing to the government through taxation in Nigerian. The study employed secondary data that cover a period from 2000 to 2018. Multi-regression analysis was performed and the results indicated that corruption was very harmful to tax revenue collection while the informal economy has no significant impact on tax revenue within the millennium period covered by this study.

Olabisi, et al., (2020) investigates the effect of informal sector tax proceeds on capital development in Lagos Metropolis. The study adopted Ex-post facto design to obtain secondary data, covering 20 years (2000–2019). Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression was used to revealed that tax collected had a significant effect on capital development in Lagos Metropolis, which is evident from the monumental capital projects being executed by the government in the Metropolis. to the capital development of the Metropolis through tax revenue.

Similarly, Awa (2022) examined the effect of informal sector tax revenue on capital growth in Ebonyi State Capital, Abakaliki. The study adopted Ex-post facto research design while secondary data, covering 21 years (2000–2020) were obtained from the State Internal Revenue Service . Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression was employed to revealed that tax collected Market men and women had a significant effect on capital growth in Abakaliki, the State Capital. This is evident from the monumental capital projects being executed by the government in Abakaliki, the capital city.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried in Osun State Southwest Nigeria's. Osun is One regional commercial hub for both agricultural and manufactured items from various parts of the nation. Osun State is made up of a mix of urban and rural structures that are distinguished by forms of taxes revenue from informal sectors. This study employed ex post-facto research design. This is because data needed for analysis already exists. The population of this study consisted of data collected from the Osun State Internal Revenue Service Board and Ministry of Finance. Hence, this type of study does not require any sampling as it wholly involves secondary data that are readily available. Secondary data were obtained from obtained from Osun State Internal Revenue Service Board and Ministry of Finance for a period of 9 years 2015 to 2023. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression techniques were employed in this study in addition to relevant diagnostic tests

Model Specification

$$CAEXP = f(TMT, TPT) \tag{1}$$

Equation (3.4) can be expressed in stochastic for as

$$CAEXP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MARK_t + \beta_1 TPT_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{2}$$

Where,

β_0 = Constant Parameter: β_1 = Regression Coefficient of Variables

$CAPE_t$ = Capital expenditure

TMT = Taxes from market traders

TPT= Taxes from petty traders

ε = Stochastic Error term, t = time

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graphical Presentation

Figure 1: Trends of Taxes from Market Traders 2016-2024

Measurement of Variables as expected sign *A Priori*

Table .1. Measurement of Variables

Variables	Variable Labels	Measurement	Expected sign	Expected sign
Dependent Variables				
Capital expenditure	CAPE	capital expenditure incurred on capital project	Ebipre and Eniekezimene (2020)	
Independent Variables				
Taxes from market traders	TMT	Actual Amount generated	Awa (2022) Olabisi et al., (2020)	+/-ve
Taxes from petty traders	TPT	Actual Amount generated	Awa (2022) Olabisi et al., (2020)	+/-ve

Source: *Author's Compilation, 2025*

The diagram in Figure 1 shows trend of zig-zag and moving steady from year (2016) to year (2017) and dropped in year 2016 gradually to year (2017) and picked up moving in year 2019 and sharply tax revenue from market traders dropped in 2020, this may be due to COVID 19 pandemic where some market traders were unable to engage in market activities and steadily picked up in 2023 and 2024 respectively.

Figure 1: Trends of Taxes from Petty Traders 2016-2024

Figure 2: Trends of Taxes from Petty Traders 2016-2024

The diagram in Figure 2 keeps moved on zig-zag steady from year (2016) to year (2017) and dropped between year 2019 and 2020 but tax revenue from petty traders sharply rises in 2021 and steadily picked up in 2023 and 2024 respectively.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	CAPE	TMT	TPT
Mean	2.82E+10	11081325	1276163.
Median	2.84E+10	11217451	1208179.
Maximum	3.95E+10	24369875	2272060.
Minimum	1.84E+10	1874232.	168113.4
Std. Dev.	8.05E+09	7583657.	727565.5
Skewness	0.200302	0.359564	-0.221614
Kurtosis	1.667494	2.157211	1.938047
Jarque-Bera	0.726021	0.460289	0.496574
Probability	0.695579	0.794419	0.780136
Sum	2.53E+11	99731928	11485470
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.18E+20	4.60E+14	4.23E+12
Observations	9	9	9

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Based on the data analysed in Table 2, The Table demonstrated that the respective means for CAPE 28.2 billion naira with min and max of 1.84 billion and 3.95 billion naira respectively. The average value of TMT showed 11.8 million naira while min and max 1.8 million naira and 24.36 million naira respectively. The average of taxes from petty trader found to be 1.2 million with max, of 2.2 million and mini of 0.16 million naira respectively

Skewness measurements refer to the symmetry of the series' distribution around its mean. A normal distribution has zero skewness. Almost of parameters (0.2003 and 0.3595) have positive skewness, which suggests that the distribution has long tail except TPT that had negative

Correlation Analysis

Table: 3 Correlation Matrix with Variance Inflation Factor

Table: 3 Correlation Matrix with Variance Inflation Factor

	CAPE	TMT	TPT	VIF
CAP	1.0000			NA
TMT	0.5422	1.0000		1.1137
TPT	0.1627	0.3195	1.0000	1.1137

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From result Table 3, it showed that taxes from market traders had positive and strong correlation with capital expenditure given coefficient of 0.5422, which implies that TMT contribute to CAPE in the state. Taxes from petty traders had a weak and positive correlated given the coefficient of 0.1627 . The level of multi-collinearity between the independent and dependent variables was not high, and this is affirmed by VIF that there is no issues of multicollinearity since that value did not above the threshold of 10.0

Table 4. Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Remarks
C	2.11E1	5.55E9	3.8012	0.0090	
TMT	697.8282	349.9495	1.9941	0.0932	+Sign
TPT	523.4467	3647.639	0.1435	0.8906	+Insign

	Diagnostic Tests
R-squared	0.4145
Adjusted R ²	0.2193
F-statistic	2.1238
Prob(F-statistic)	0.2007
Wald Test	4.2477
P- value	0.1196
Hetero Test	0.9739
P- value	0.4302
Serial Corr. LM T	0.0331
P-value	0.9676

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

The result presented in Table 4 showed that taxes from market traders (t-v= 1.994, p<0.01) had positive and significant effect of capital expenditure in Osun state. This implies that taxes collected from market traders (men and women) contributed positively to capital expenditure in Osun state. The result further disclosed that taxes collected from petty traders had positive and insignificant effect on capital expenditure given (t-v= 0.1435, p>0.05). This indicated that money collected from formal sector, such as fruits, vegetables, groundnuts, biscuits, spoons, pans, cigarettes, cosmetics, jewellery, and ladies' bags and wallets has no significant effect on CAPE. The result in Table 4 revealed that the R2 value of 0.41, explanatory variable composition in the capital expenditure was 41%. The remaining 59 percent is caused by variables that are not included in the model, which is accounted for by the stochastic error term. Also, result of serial correlation of p- value 0.9697 indicated non existence of auto serial correlation. The study found that there was no presence of heteroscedasticity in the study

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding from this study showed that TMT and CAPE had positive and significant effect on capital expenditure. This implies that IGR generated through market traders (men and women) have contributed significantly to capital expenditure in Osun State. This finding is consistent with outcome. Olabisi et al., (2020) revealed that tax collected from market traders had a significant effect on capital expenditure in Lagos Metropolis. Similarly, Awa (2022) revealed that tax collected

market men and women had a significant effect on capital growth in Abakaliki, the State Capital. This is evident from the monumental capital projects being executed by the government in Abakaliki, the capital city. Similar result established from the study of Obara and Nangih (2017) revealed that taxing the informal sector boosted revenue generation and positively affected the economic expenditure of developing states in Nigeria. Okereke and Olewe (2023) established that internally-generated revenue had a significant effect on the provision of road infrastructure while. In contrary, Hammayo et al. (2022) found that internally generated revenue showed a negative and significant relationship with provision of infrastructure. However, the finding indicated that taxes from petty traders had no significant effect on capital expenditure. This outcome is in contrary with the findings of Awa (2022) revealed that tax collected from petty traders had a significant effect on capital growth in Abakaliki, the State Capital.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concluded that taxes from inform sector (market traders) had significant effect on capital expenditure of Osun state while taxes collected from petty traders had no effect. The study recommended that tax collection from the informal sector (market traders) could be enhanced when government educates the informal operators, strengthens tax laws, emphasize on adequate records. Government should create an enabling environment for the informal sector (market men and women) and petty traders) to thrive and to give all necessary assistance/support for its survival

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